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D.6.6

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Executive Summary

INFRAMIX will help prepare road infrastructure to support the coexistence of conventional and automated vehicles. Its main objective is to design, upgrade, adapt and test both physical and digital elements of the road infrastructure. The key outcome will be a “hybrid” road infrastructure able to handle the transition period and become the basis for future automated transport systems. The project developments will be assessed via simulation and on real stretches of advanced highways. This will help to ensure that the proposed adaptations will not jeopardize safety, efficiency and quality of service and will be appreciated by the users.

INFRAMIX Project activities have set ambitious targets for the adaptation of existing road infrastructure for the adoption of the automated vehicle. A concise dissemination strategy, therefore, is of major importance for the maximization of the project’s impact to the scientific community, the industry, the society and for the successful deployment of its results. The consortium’s intention is to widely disseminate the existence of the project goals and results not only within Europe but also internationally, in order to highlight Europe as a major force worldwide in the relevant scientific and industrial field. In this document, the communication and dissemination strategy and plans designed for this purpose are presented.

This is the second update of the communication strategy and plan for INFRAMIX project. As described in the DoA, in order to keep the alignment of the communication strategy with the findings and results of the project as well as the impact of the previous dissemination actions, this deliverable, original produced in M6 has been revised in M18. A final update will be prepared for M36.

The purpose of this new version is to report actions executed during the first 18 months, analysing and evaluating the impact of the strategy and plan in order to readapt them, if necessary.

The new content affects mainly to sections:

- Section 3.9 - End users
- Section 5.4.1 - Newsletter
- Section 7.3 - External events
- Section 8 - Measuring the effectiveness of activities
- Section 9 - Conclusion

In this deliverable, after the execution of the strategy and plan designed for the INFRAMIX project during M1-M18 period, the results and the assessment of the impact have been analysed.

The general conclusion is that the performance and impact of the dissemination and communication strategy for INFRAMIX project during the first period (M1-M18) has been aligned with the initial expectations. Most of the KPIs (Key Performance Indicator) have been successfully achieved and even overcome in some cases. The INFRAMIX partners have been very active while presenting the project in several scenarios and to different stakeholders at any level. However, it is necessary to highlight some questions:

- Impact has been created but very focused on some countries. This should be re-addressed by enhancing the collaboration among the partners in the consortium
- The LinkedIn communication channel (INFRAMIX group) can generate additional impact if it could work as a discussion forum.

Beyond these aspects, no major questions or changes of the communication and dissemination strategy are expected for the following months.

1. Introduction

1.1 Aim of the project

INFRAMIX will help prepare road infrastructure to support the coexistence of conventional and automated vehicles.

Its main objective is to design, upgrade, adapt and test both physical and digital elements of the road infrastructure. The key outcome will be a “hybrid” road infrastructure able to handle the transition period and become the basis for future automated transport systems. The project developments will be assessed via simulation and on real stretches of advanced highways. This will help to ensure that the proposed adaptations will not jeopardize safety, efficiency, quality of service and will be appreciated by the users.

INFRAMIX builds on three traffic scenarios: *dynamic lane assignment*, *roadwork zones* and *bottlenecks*. INFRAMIX addresses mainly highways, as they are expected to be the initial hosts of mixed traffic, but the key results can also be transferred to urban roads.

1.2 Purpose of document

This is the second update of the communication strategy and plan for INFRAMIX project. As described in the DoA, in order to keep the alignment of the communication strategy with the findings and results of the project as well as the impact of the previous dissemination actions, this deliverable, original produced in M6 has been revised in M18. A final update will be prepared for M36.

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INFRAMIX Project activities have set ambitious targets for the adaptation of existing road infrastructure for the adoption of the automated vehicle. A concise dissemination strategy, therefore, is of major importance for the maximization of the project’s impact to the scientific community, the industry, the society and for the successful deployment of its results. The consortium’s intention is to widely disseminate the existence of the project goals and results not only within Europe but also internationally, in order to highlight Europe as a major force worldwide in the relevant scientific and industrial field. In this document, the communication and dissemination strategy and plans designed for this purpose are presented.

The dissemination strategy defines the goals for the dissemination activities of the project. These are being achieved by reaching the specified dissemination target groups through defined dissemination channels. The ways to reach the target groups depends on the stage of the work progress of the project. While at the early stages of the project the dissemination is concentrated on presentations of the idea and concept of the work to be deployed, at later stages the dissemination task will focus on presenting the achieved developments and

results. All these are described in the dissemination roadmap which provides a draft outline of the dissemination activities and their presented content per year of the project.

Dissemination activities are important for the Consortium also on a partner level. Making the Consortium partners' competencies known can prove beneficial for promoting their activities as well. It is expected that regardless the partnership in the specific project WP, all partners will take part in Communication and Dissemination activities even at a different level. This contribution can take several forms, from artistic design in the dissemination material to scientific review of papers in workshops, conference participation, exhibitions etc. Thus, it is essential that all partners have an overall idea of their planned dissemination activities either for INFRAMIX purposes exclusively or for general purposes where INFRAMIX will also be represented. The dissemination activities are managed by the Dissemination Leader and specific dissemination procedures are followed which are also described within the document.

2. General Communication and Dissemination Objectives

2.1 Background

The overall aim of the INFRAMIX communication and dissemination framework is to promote the project, its mission and results to a wide range of stakeholders at European, national, regional, local and international levels. It is important to communicate with a far-reaching audience and each level of governance has different stakeholders which INFRAMIX needs to address. Therefore, the project will adopt a cross-level dissemination approach.

The project also aims to establish the project and its tools as a reference point for the adaptation of existing road infrastructure for the adoption of the automated vehicle. This aspect is increasingly important for the legacy of the project and aims to encourage the actual take-up and deployment of the INFRAMIX solution after the project has finished.

A key objective of INFRAMIX is to develop effective communication interfaces and dissemination channels. All of the dissemination tools will have a clear message and explain the objectives and mission of the project in a consistent and coherent way. All of the separate communication tools (described later) aim to attract the interest of all of the target groups and are designed to match the common project identity.

The project also aims to communicate the role of the EU and the H2020 Programme through all the communication and dissemination channels. It is important to promote the programme supporting INFRAMIX and showcase similar successful projects to boost the overall success of the project.

2.2 Dissemination Objectives

As said before, the overall objective is to promote the project, its mission and results to the groups of stakeholders described in Section 3, and achieve the largest possible impact, to build consensus and to raise awareness around the achievements of innovations and best practices developed in the project, and to exploit the results to benefit the implementation of the INFRAMIX key innovations.

Through different targeted activities and dedicated communication tools, the INFRAMIX Dissemination Strategy includes the following:

- Define a dissemination framework, with dedicated dissemination tools and channels which are adapted to respective target groups;
- Organise and facilitate events with input from all WPs;
- Establish synergy in dissemination with relevant other initiatives;
- Present INFRAMIX at internal and external events.

3. Communication and Dissemination target groups

3.1 Industry

This group includes the following sub-groups:

- OEMs / Vehicle manufacturers
- Vehicle technology suppliers
- Infrastructure technology suppliers
- Other ICT solutions providers

This group comprises both business and technical experts. The communication direction can be both external to the consortium and internal towards the project partners.

3.2 Infrastructure operators and Road authorities

This group includes the organizations (public or private) responsible for the correct managing of the road infrastructure. It includes both individual organizations and/or associations (ERF, CEDR, ASECAP, ERTRAC, BAST¹, etc).

3.3 Public administration

It refers to the decision makers, city planners and other public authorities at different geographical levels, as urban areas, regional administrations, countries and different country clusters. They can be responsible for the design, construction, operation and/or legislation of the road transportation in public infrastructures.

3.4 Relevant EU, national and international initiatives

Dissemination within the research community is one of the pre-requisites for successful project implementation. Knowledge exchange is crucial for assessing the state-of-the-art, project planning and evaluating project results.

This target group will be addressed via different ways: individually, within the framework of international organisations in which researchers maintain international exchange and cooperation, and by official contact at project level.

Some of the potential projects are as follows:

- AutoMate, www.automate-project.eu
- BRAVE, www.brave-project.eu
- CARTRE/ARCADE, www.connectedautomateddriving.eu/about-us/cartre;
<https://connectedautomateddriving.eu/arcade-project/>
- CoEXist, www.h2020-coexist.eu
- ConVeX, www.qualcomm.com/news/onq/2017/02/24/accelerating-c-v2x-toward-5g-autonomous-driving
- Dragon, www.cedr-dragon.eu
- interACT, www.interact-roadautomation.eu

¹ Bundesanstalt für Straßenwesen (german federal organisation for street management)

- L3Pilot, l3pilot.eu
- MAVEN, www.maven-its.eu
- PROVIDENTIA, www.fortiss.org/forschung/projekte/providentia/
- SCOUT, www.connectedautomateddriving.eu/about-us/scout/
- SENSKIN, www.senskin.eu
- TRAMAN21, www.traman21.tuc.gr
- TransAID, www.transaid.eu
- TrustVehicle, www.trustvehicle.eu

This effort will have an international scope. European, but also overseas high-profile colleagues involved in similar research activities will be contacted for collaboration.

3.5 Standardisation bodies

This target group will focus on entities as European Telecommunications Standards Institute, ETSI, or Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE).

3.6 European and international organisations and technical communities

This is a wide group of individual associations (i.e. industry associations as EUCAR, OICA, ACEA, VDA, ANFAC, SAE; other relevant EC/national projects; ETP's such as ERTRAC; technology groups as FEHRL, ERTICO, Amsterdam Group, C2C-CC, TM2.0 Platform, ADASIS Forum, NDS Association, AASHTO, FHWA, AUVSI, TRB and the Trilateral EU-US-Japan Automation Working Group in Road Transportation), at European, national and international level, which have significant multiplier potential as associations representing transport authorities and members of the industry.

3.7 Scientific and research community

The results of the project will be broadly disseminated to the scientific community through participation in the most important academic conferences and related events. Please refer to section 7.3 for a detailed list of events.

3.8 EC staff/politicians and relevant European Organizations

This group includes EC staff/politicians, relevant European Organizations (ERTICO, etc), policy advisors and key opinion creators.

This will facilitate a clearer overall understanding of the topic and consequently will provide an evident support for decision making activities at higher level.

This group includes standardization fora and initiatives where the results and project recommendations will be communicated.

3.9 End users

The following target groups have been identified up to now: Drivers associations; Professional transport associations; Safety groups:

- IRU World Transport Organization (www.iru.org).

- Association for European Transport (www.aetransport.org).
- Drivers associations at global level as FIA (www.fia.com) or FIM (www.fim-live.com) or national/regional level (as, for example, RACE Real Automovil Club España – www.race.es - or RACC Real Automovil Club Catalunya - www.racc.es).
- ETSC European Transport Safety Council (www.etsc.eu).
- MOVINGs International Safety Association (www.moving-roadsafety.com).
- ADAC (www.adac.de).
- ERTICO TM2.0 platform.
- Conference of European Directors of Roads (CEDR).
- European Road Transport Research Advisory Council (ERTRAC).
- the Italian group of the world road association (AIPCR).
- 3M (www.mmm.com).
- Managing Automated Vehicles Enhances Network (MAVEN).
- Transition Areas for Infrastructure -Assisted Driving (TransAID).
- Preparing the transition phase during which automated and conventional vehicles will co-exist on cities' roads (CoEXist).
- Risk Assessment on Danube Area Roads /RADAR).
- trilateral cooperation of road operators in AUT/SLO/HUN.

3.10 Key influencers / Publications

EU wide, national, regional, online and specialist publications. Please refer to section 5.2.3 for a detailed list of publications.

3.11 General public

Informing and communicating with the public as well as fostering societal debate have already become integral constituents of the portfolio of European initiatives. For this audience, key-messages should focus on the overall concept rather than on specific technical solutions.

4. Communication and Dissemination Plan

The selection of the appropriate dissemination channel and the respective message to be disseminated heavily depends on the stage that the project is at each specific moment. During the early phases of the project, the focus is on transmitting the project concept and the idea of the research work. Towards the end of the project, however, more technical presentations and publications can be realised as new findings will be available. Having this in mind, the Communication and Dissemination plan has been determined and is presented below. This Plan provides the outline of how the dissemination channels and materials will be used for reaching each of the specified target group per year of the project.

Figure 1 – Phases of the activities

4.1 First phase activities

During the first part of the project, the dissemination activities are aiming to generally inform the public, relevant research, academic and automated vehicle community and all relevant stakeholders on INFRAMIX objectives and expected results. These activities are setting the basis for the whole communication and dissemination policy since most of the communication and dissemination material will be produced at this stage and will be used for the duration of the project. The informative leaflets and roll-up have been designed and are going to be disseminated to various events. In addition, the website has already been developed including information about the project and it will be updated regularly. The publications and presentations of this period describe mainly the project's concept and research methodology. At this stage, the main activities are related mostly to Communication, rather than Dissemination.

This phase covers from project's start to first findings obtained, approximately in M18.

4.2 Second phase activities

During the second part of the project, some results will already be available. Thus, the aim of the communication and dissemination activities within this period will be to publish the first findings and describe the future work to be performed. The research community, industry and policy-making authorities and decision-making stakeholders, end users etc., will form the target groups of the publications and project presentations to be performed during this phase. Technical papers will be submitted to scientific conferences as well as to workshops and events. The communication and dissemination material will be the same as developed in the first phase while the website will be continuously updated with newer project achievements.

This phase covers from first findings to completion of the set of tools, approximately in M29.

4.3 Third phase activities

During the final part of the project there will be a major effort of disseminating the project results to all target groups using every dissemination channel available. Press releases and mass media will be employed for transmitting the INFRAMIX message. Technical papers presenting the final results will be published to journals and to various international and

European industry and scientific conferences, while demonstrations of solutions and prototypes will be given at relevant exhibitions. At this phase several papers submissions to scientific journals are expected. The website will continuously be updated with the latest developments and information and the final project deliverables will be available for downloading.

4.4 Activities after the project end

Even after the end of the project, there is still a possibility to support and promote the project impact to the wider community. All public final results will be available at INFRAMIX web site. It will be sustained after the end of the project for at least five years in order to provide all interested stakeholders with information on project achievements and findings and details on contact persons for more information.

4.5 Time table of results

The table below includes the planned timeline for the availability of the project findings, as well as the expected communicable results and the respective audience addressed:

Table 1 - INFRAMIX results along timeline

Id	Time	Date	Expected results	Audience addressed
R1	M06	Nov'17	- Requirements catalogue, Analysis of the three traffic scenarios and definition of related use cases resulting in requirements	- Industry - Infrastructure operators, road authorities - Relevant initiatives - General Public
R2	M18	Nov'18	- Simulations tools and relevant models ready - Traffic state estimation and traffic control algorithms available - Plan for demonstrations and testing finalized	- Industry - Infrastructure operators, road authorities - Relevant initiatives - EC&EU authorities - Influencers
R3	M24	May'19	- Digital and physical infrastructure elements designed and developed - New visual signs and elements - HD maps and electronic road horizon (*) - Traffic management strategies (*)	- Industry - Infrastructure operators, road authorities - Relevant initiatives - EC&EU authorities - Influencers
R4	M26	Jul'19	- Infrastructure classification scheme available	- Industry - Infrastructure operators, road authorities - Relevant initiatives - EC&EU authorities
R5	M30	Nov'19	- Aggregated data available for evaluation (*)	- Industry - Infrastructure operators, road authorities
R6	M36	May'20	- Evaluation, impact analysis and	- Industry

Id	Time	Date	Expected results	Audience addressed
			users' appreciation results - Exploitation plans (*) - Roadmap towards fully automated transport systems	- Infrastructure operators, road authorities - Relevant initiatives - EC&EU authorities - Influencers - General Public

(*) These results may contain confidential information. Each of them will be analysed to define the public contents; at the same time, the existence and purpose itself of the result could be of use in the communication activities.

Additional new results have been analysed during the preparation of the Exploitation Plans. Due to their confidential nature, it is not possible to include them in this document, but they may be checked in INFRAMIX D6.5 Exploitation Plans.

5. Communication and Dissemination tools

The communication and dissemination toolbox is divided in several sections:

- Establishing INFRAMIX as a brand
- Mass media
- On-line tools

These elements will be elaborated in the following sections. The related initial material described in these sections is presented in the document INFRAMIX D6.2 Communications kit.

5.1 Establishing INFRAMIX as a brand

The following table summarises the subjects (further described later) with the related results and the expected audience:

Table 2 - INFRAMIX communication tools and audience groups

Subject	Related Results	Audience								
		Industry	Infr. Ops & Road auth	Public admin	EU&Nat org and Tech	Scientific & R+I com.	EC and EU stakeh	End users	Key influencers	General public
Logo	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Roll-up	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Brochure	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
General presentation	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	

5.1.1 Project Logo

A logo (abbreviation of logotype) is a graphic mark, emblem, or symbol commonly used to aid and promote instant public recognition.

The project logo (Figure 2) has been produced electronically in high-definition PNG format.

Figure 2 – Logo

5.1.2 Project brochure

Description

Project brochure is a presentation of the project concept, challenges and characteristics of developed solutions. It should be presented with the use of graphics, pictures, icons and graphs reflecting the project idea.

Use:

INFRAMIX brochure illustrates the project's concept, proposed solutions and expected impact. It has been produced electronically in PDF format and is available on the project website. An English version will be printed and will be used in every available occasion - at INFRAMIX events and meetings with stakeholders as well as at external events such as conferences, fairs and exhibitions, seminars and other meetings with industry. The content of this brochure will be updated during the project, if necessary, to include final INFRAMIX results.

The electronic version could be produced in different languages (based on the requests and availability of the partners of the project) to reach the widest possible target audience in several countries. Since the purpose of the brochure is to have a lifespan that will encompass the whole duration of the project it will be written in an open style, so that it is fresh and appealing for catching the audience.

We estimate to distribute 1.000 brochures during the different events where INFRAMIX and/or INFRAMIX partners could participate.

5.1.3 General presentation

Description

The general project presentation is an electronic presentation composed by several general slides introducing the main project idea. The text is in most cases presented in bullet points accompanied by pictures, icons, links to websites, etc.

Use:

The general project presentation will be used during different events, including internal project events such as project workshops, meetings with stakeholders and external events such as conferences, fairs and exhibitions and seminars. The purpose is to assist partners to communicate INFRAMIX solutions, expected impact and at a later stage initial achievements and results, in a consolidated and consistent way both internally and externally. The presentation will be made in English and should be translated into other partners' languages if needed for the communication with the stakeholders in partner countries.

5.1.4 Roll-up banner and posters

Description

The project roll-ups and posters are large one-page graphical presentations or pictures of the project idea. The design of project roll-ups and posters is of high relevance and therefore it must follow the "corporate identity" pattern (logo, images, colours, fonts). Its purpose is to capture attention and advertise the project. Its basic content should include:

- Acronym and name of the project
- Logos and tagline for the project

Use

During the project, roll-ups and posters will be designed for specific events or purposes. They will be used to provide an eye-catching and thought-provoking presentation, and to include contact or website details giving ready access to further information. It will be printed and used at exhibitions, conferences and public meetings.

5.2 Media

The following table summarises the media related measures (described later in detail) with the related results and the expected audience:

Table 3 - INFRAMIX media tools and audience groups

Measures	Related Results	Audience								
		Industry	Infr. Ops & Road auth	Public admin	EU&Nat org and Tech	Scientific & R+I com.	EC and EU stakeh	End users	Key influencers	General public
Promotional video(s)	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Press releases	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Generalist Journals publications	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Specialised Journals publications	General communication / Focused results	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

5.2.1 Promotional video

Description

The project video is an interactive presentation in the form of a movie briefly introducing the project idea, its results and characteristics of developed solutions using simple messages.

Use

It is presented in English and is available through the project’s web site and other available channels, platforms such as YouTube, forums supporting the project realisation and in social media.

The video will be enriched in the course of project including actual developments demonstrated at the INFRAMIX test sites. The different versions of the INFRAMIX video will be also displayed both at INFRAMIX events and at relevant conferences and exhibitions.

5.2.2 Press releases

Description

Press releases are intended to communicate the project’s progress or announce important achievements. A press release is usually a one-page note presenting the message briefly, using simple language.

Use

All project members are expected to contribute to the dissemination of project results through appropriate press releases in their respective countries throughout the duration of the project. Especially WP leaders are requested to produce press releases on the results achieved. When such a press release is published, an electronic copy must be sent to the dissemination leader, in order to be uploaded to the project website. In addition, some

details should be given by the partner in charge: source, publication date, target audience.

A press release template will be included as part of INFRAMIX D6.2 Communications kit.

5.2.3 Sectorial Newspapers/Journals publications

Description

Publication of the project in Newspapers and Journals in the form of articles (not advertisement).

Use

The project partners will be asked to explore the possibility to present the project in sectorial Newspapers/Journals according to the cost/benefit principle.

List of potential business and scientific journals (to be expanded during the project):

Table 4 – Initial list of business and scientific Journals

Business and Scientific Journals	Comment
Horizon Magazine	
Research*eu results magazine	
Futuris Magazine	
Thinking Highways	
IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Magazine (ITSM)	
ITS International	
International Journal of Vehicle Autonomous Systems	Possible open access
SAE Connected and Automated Vehicles	
SAE Automotive Engineering	
Springer - Journal of Modern Transportation	Possible open access
Intelligent Transport – Magazine	
Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems	Possible open access
Traffic Engineering and Control (TEC) magazine	
Traffic Technology International	
Intertraffic World	
Routes/Roads - World Road Association	
www.worldhighways.com	
Automotive News	
IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters (GRSL)	
GeoInformatics Magazine	
ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information	Possible open access
IEEE Spectrum	General Technical Scope
Open Science Journal	General Technical Scope
R&D Magazine - rdmag.com	General Technical Scope
Science Business	General Technical Scope

During the first year, INFRAMIX plans to publish at least 3 scientific papers in international journals or conferences. Please check section 8.1 for extended KPI figures.

5.3 On-line tools

In this section, several on-line tools are reviewed. For each one, an analysis is performed to define its potential use related to the objectives of the internet community presence of INFRAMIX; the final goal is to select the most suitable ones, describing the potential use of them.

The following table summarises the on-line tools related measures (further described later)

with the related results and the expected audience:

Table 5 - INFRAMIX online tools and audience groups

Measures	Related Results	Audience								
		Industry	Infr. Ops & Road auth	Public admin	EU&Nat org and Tech	Scientific & R+I com.	EC and EU stakeh	End users	Key influencers	General public
Web site	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Newsletters	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Social media	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

5.4 Website

Description

As stated in the INFRAMIX Description of Work, the project website is a major channel for visibility of the INFRAMIX project: it describes the project and its aims and highlights its results to be achieved. The project website also serves as an interactive tool for internal and external communication. It provides a place to share public documents, updates on the current research phases and results, presents further developments and informs about upcoming events.

Use

As mentioned before, the website (www.inframix.eu) will be the key stone for the building of the internet community for INFRAMIX. It will centralize the content provided from the project among the other web 2.0 tools, trying to organize a common approach among all them and taking profit of the different features of the others.

Recognizing that the project website/portal is an important resource in disseminating information about the project, facilitating collaboration amongst partners, and bringing together a diverse and scattered community of interest around the project's activities, we have foreseen the following activities to improve its usability and features, and to market it for increased traffic and searchability:

Figure 1 INFRAMIX web site www.inframix.eu

- Improving and updating content to be relevant and rich in keywords density;
- Introducing Search Engine Marketing parameters such as keyword density, quality titles, headers and images, etc.
- A Sign In online form for people interested in the topics of INFRAMIX is included in every page to subscribe and receive INFRAMIX updates and newsletters. This way, the website will serve also as one of the channels that will be used for the expansion of the INFRAMIX End Users' Group.
- A download area has also been created, where public project deliverables, open access publications, presentations, newsletters, press articles and communication material will be available for download.

The goal is to make the portal a true source of information and contact point for further collaboration. The website content will be kept simple so as to be understandable by non-technical audiences too and will include details on the project vision, concept, objectives, proposed technologies, consortium members, test sites and expected impact.

During the first year, we have the goal of 250 unique page views per month, enabled by the mentioned actions as well as SEO (Search Engine Optimization) techniques. Please check section 8.1 for extended KPI figures.

Community Manager

To execute this strategy and to mobilize the different efforts to provide contents and materials for all these tools, it is necessary to define a single responsible for these activities. This role will need:

- To be aware of the technical and scientific activities and findings of the project;
- To be aware of the different dissemination actions of the project;
- To channelize the feedback received from the audience;
- To coordinate the consortium partners to enhance the impact of the dissemination tools;
- To gather all this information to provide contents and materials for the Web tools, especially creating an open discussion around the concepts of the project.

The Dissemination manager will initially act as Community Manager of INFRAMIX.

5.4.1 Newsletter

Description

A newsletter is a regularly distributed publication generally about one main topic that is of interest to its subscribers. Newspapers and leaflets are types of newsletters. Additionally, newsletters delivered electronically via email (e-Newsletters) have gained rapid acceptance for the same reasons as email, in general, has gained popularity over printed correspondence. Newsletters have become common source of informing specific audience on issues of their interest.

Sending newsletters to customers is a common marketing strategy, which can have benefits and drawbacks. General attributes of newsletters include news and upcoming events of the related organization, as well as contact information for general inquiries.

Use

The project newsletter is a very important tool for the communication of the project goals. Concerning the use for the internet community building, a double method will be used: 1) the existing versions are available on the website; 2) it is actively distributed through the social media, through a specific mailing list and, also, through the project consortium partners.

The INFRAMIX newsletters are oriented to offer information to project stakeholders, focusing on aims and results instead of on project's internal organization or activities. In each newsletter we include the most important highlights (in terms of results) during the period covered.

The INFRAMIX newsletter will be released per semester, therefore a total of five e-newsletters will be produced, one every six months (starting in M12) during the project to keep the INFRAMIX community informed about the project's progress and results. Short and snappy articles on the project's activities and demonstrations will give a good impression to the different target groups INFRAMIX intends to reach including the members of the INFRAMIX End User Group, as well as non-technical audiences via social media and direct emailing. The newsletter will also provide an opportunity to expand the project's database via the subscription option on the INFRAMIX website.

Table 6 – Schedule of newsletters for INFRAMIX project

Number	Due date
E-newsletter 1	July 2018
E-newsletter 2	November 2018
E-newsletter 3	June 2019
E-newsletter 4	December 2019
E-newsletter 5	May 2020

The related KPI include the newsletter distributed to 50 signed persons at M12, achieved through a mix of actions on the website and other social media. Please check section 8.1 for extended KPI figures.

Please check Annexes section for additional information about data privacy handling concerning Newsletter and mailing lists management.

5.4.2 Social media

Next to classic electronic channels like email and a web portal, Social Media need consideration. Because of the ease of communication and the groups involved, the dynamics of communication will be intense, and messages can get warped if conversations are left alone, once INFRAMIX news have been picked up by certain Social Media. Social Media will be applied in specific situations like indicated hereafter:

- Twitter (@INFRAMIX): to be applied at specific conferences and workshops, using a hashtag assigned by the conference/workshop organizer. The '#INFRAMIX' combined with a hashtag of the conference/workshop will be used for specific workshops.
- LinkedIn (INFRAMIX Project, <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12078841>): will be used to create interest groups with focused discussions and to post blogs and newsfeeds.

Other social media such as YouTube, SlideShare or Wikipedia are considered in Annexes section.

Two social media campaigns will be organised in the course of the project. The campaigns will aim to involve interested stakeholders in the ongoing discussion regarding the need for improving road infrastructure to facilitate the gradual insertion of automated vehicles on our roads and be prepared for mixed traffic scenarios. Social media activities will also assist partners to identify and invite interested experts to join the INFRAMIX End Users' Group.

Furthermore, the consortium members will make use of their companies'/organisations'

individual social networking sites to diffuse project messages and discuss project innovations and proposed solutions with their contacts. INFRAMIX consortium will also seek every opportunity to diffuse project achievements through the H2020 related social media accounts.

During the first year, we have about 160 twitter followers reached by cross following actions, and 50 LinkedIn group members, achieved through an activity and collaboration of the Consortium members professional accounts, as well as communication of the addresses using posters, flyers, website, etc. Please check section 8.1 for extended KPI figures.

5.5 Project wrap-up and preparing for exploitation

This final phase of the project will present the overall results of the INFRAMIX project. The final event will be the main opportunity to showcase the INFRAMIX results. This event will also be the start of the post-project INFRAMIX take-up.

5.6 Dissemination versus Communication channels²

Table 7 – Dissemination versus communication channels

Channels	Communication	Dissemination
Project website – General presentation pages	X	
Project website – Specific pages dedicated to outputs		X
Mailing lists & Contact databases – General	X	X
Social media	X	
External channels – Generalist	X	
External channels – Specialised, sectorial, targeted		X
Project events – Presentation of project outputs		X
External events – Announcements, brochures and flyers, etc	X	
External events – Presentation of project results		X
Publications in scientific magazines		X

² For a discussion concerning the differences between Dissemination and Communication in the H2020 arena, please check Annex concerning H2020 Guidelines

6. Dissemination toolbox

6.1 Dissemination approval procedure

Following the INFRAMIX Consortium Agreement, a procedure for the approval for publication of scientific/technical materials has been defined. Please refer to the Annex section for a detailed description.

6.2 Open access

Article 29.2 of the Grant Agreement states that “*each beneficiary **MUST ensure open access** (free of charge, online access for any user) to ALL peer reviewed scientific publication relating its results.*” INFRAMIX will apply two different models:

- Green model. After an embargo period benefiting the publisher, the scientific author/s publishes the article/paper in an open repository.
- Gold model. The scientific author allows (i.e. by payment) to the publisher to allow immediate open access to readers.

A major effort will be made to address the publication of peer-reviewed scientific papers and articles to renowned and high-impact journals and conferences proceedings. As said, INFRAMIX will pursue a hybrid approach regarding the specific open access model it will follow (see Figure 3). It will sustain the Green Model (self-archiving) for the majority of its publications, while for 2 or 3 key publications, such as the infrastructure classification scheme, it will follow the Gold model (open access publishing). The reasoning behind this hybrid approach is the publication fees associated with the Gold model, which are not negligible. Thus, for the latter case, dedicated resources have been allocated in the budget breakdown.

The intention of the project, in line with the spirit of Horizon 2020, is to promote INFRAMIX scientific results in an open access mode either through specific repositories and the INFRAMIX project website (in case of Green Model) or directly by exploiting the scientific publisher resources (in case of Gold Model). Concurrently, the project will apply the Creative Commons Attribution Licence to published work to allow its download, read, print, distribution, copy and use, as long as the original authors and source are cited. The INFRAMIX website is the communication platform for the dissemination of knowledge, material and results, publishing grey literature information to the general public or to a restricted group (the consortium and the EC), in accordance to the consortium’s knowledge management and IPR policies. All INFRAMIX data (e.g. customer-sourced information) that encompass personal data protection or privacy and IPR or form the basis to the project’s business model will be stored in the project repository and will not be publicly disclosed. Following this hybrid strategy, the partnership will benefit from the proliferation of search engines and indexation techniques, while recognising OA benefits to the increased access and impact of INFRAMIX innovations, assisting an effective knowledge sharing.

Figure 3 - INFRAMIX knowledge management and protection strategy in the wider context of dissemination

6.3 Results timeline of expected communicable results

Dissemination is supported by publications, i.e., deliverables considered as public and communications to academic and technical publications and events.

The following table lists the public project deliverables, including the ID of the results that link with Table 1. Given its interest, some confidential deliverables have been also included in the table (identified with the * sign): each of them will be analysed to delimitate its public contents, if any; in addition, the mere existence and purpose itself of the result could be of use in the communication activities.

Table 8 - INFRAMIX deliverables and target groups

Div	Deliverable name	Delivery date (M)	Related Results Id	Audience									
				Industry	Infr. Ops & Road auth	Public admin	Relevant Initiatives	EU&Nat org and Tech	Scientific & R+I com.	EC and EU stakeh	End users	Key influencers	General public
D2.1	Requirements catalogue from the status quo analysis	6	R1	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			
D4.1	INFRAMIX plan for systems interaction, integration and testing	18	R2	X	X		X	X	X				
D3.1	Design and development of infrastructure elements	24	R3	X	X		X	X	X				
D3.3	HD maps and electronic road horizon (*)	24	R3	X	X		X	X	X	X			
D3.4	Implementation of traffic management strategies (*)	24	R3	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			
D3.5	New visual signs and elements	24	R3	X	X	X	X	X		X	X		
D5.4	Infrastructure classification scheme	26	R4	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			
D4.2	Demonstration phase and data delivery report (*)	30	R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			
D5.2	Users' appreciation results	36	R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
D5.3	Evaluation results, impact analysis and new safety performance criteria for the road infrastructure	36	R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
D6.4	Roadmap towards fully automated transport systems	36	R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
D6.5	Exploitation plans (*)	36	R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	

In addition, the project plans to publish 18 scientific papers in international journals or conferences. The below table shows a tentative list of schedule and contents related to these scientific papers:

Table 9 - INFRAMIX planned scientific publications

Paper Id	Issuing date	Related Results Id									
			Industry	Infr. Ops & Road auth	Public admin	Relevant Initiatives	EU&Nat org and Tech	Scientific & R+I com.	EC and EU stakeh	End users	
P1	M12	R1	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
P2	M12	R1	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
P3	M12	R1	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
P4	M24	R2	X	X		X	X	X			
P5	M24	R2	X	X		X	X	X			
P6	M24	R3	X	X		X	X	X			
P7	M24	R3	X	X		X	X	X			
P8	M24	R3	X	X		X	X	X			
P9	M24	R3	X	X		X	X	X			
P10	M24	R3	X	X		X	X	X			
P11	M36	R4	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
P12	M36	R4	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
P13	M36	R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
P14	M36	R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
P15	M36	R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
P16	M36	R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
P17	M36	R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
P18	M36	R4, R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

6.4 Related initiatives

Several initiatives, both ongoing and future will be contacted to work on cross-fertilization, to align expectation and to avoid duplicities. Among them:

- interACT (www.interact-roadautomation.eu)
- BRAVE (www.brave-project.eu)
- TrustVehicle (www.trustvehicle.eu)

- L3Pilot (www.l3pilot.eu)
- CoEXist (www.h2020-coexist.eu)
- TransAID (www.transaid.eu)
- MAVEN (www.maven-its.eu)

During the first year, we got in contact with several national or EU-scoped projects/initiatives. Please check section 8.1 for extended KPI figures.

7. INFRAMIX events and visibility at external events

The INFRAMIX events will come as a dissemination support to project objectives. They will help in spreading the project outputs to the respective target audiences, facilitate valuable feedback from respective stakeholders, and provide ground for discussion and brainstorming.

7.1 INFRAMIX events

Three major events will be organised by INFRAMIX to underpin the communication and dissemination of the project. Specifically, two **Stakeholder Workshops** will be held in **M24 at the Spanish test site** and in **M29 at the Austrian test site** aiming to efficiently disseminate preliminary findings and collect targeted feedback from key-actors.

An **INFRAMIX Conference** will be organised in Austria towards the end of the project, where INFRAMIX final results will be presented to approximately 100 attendees through technical presentations while technologies will be showcased through live demonstrations and an exhibition. A press conference will also be held in the context of the INFRAMIX final event to spread the word about project results and solutions to non-technical audiences and the media. To secure wide after-event dissemination, the workshops and final conference materials, i.e. technical presentations and reports on performed discussions, will be available at the INFRAMIX website.

7.2 INFRAMIX End Users' Group events

For engaging as many stakeholders as possible, collecting their direct feedback and efficiently disseminate project results and evolutions, an End Users' Group will be early created in the framework of Task 6.3. The Group will be open to join and will give its participants the choice of simply receiving information or being more actively involved in INFRAMIX deployment. The latter will comprise the core members of the End Users' Group. These Core members will be requested to provide direct feedback on every opportunity (i.e. through participation at INFRAMIX Stakeholder Workshops), to assist the INFRAMIX consortium to efficiently evaluate the proposed technologies and perform the required corrections according to the end user needs and expectations. This group is also expected to help in reaching consensus regarding the proposed solutions for key issues such as infrastructure classification. The aforementioned engagement activities are highly expected to increase user acceptance and in complement with the INFRAMIX exploitation activities (Task 6.4) to ensure wide market penetration of the proposed solutions. A first list of the Core End Users' Group members, willing to closely cooperate with INFRAMIX consortium, is available in M09 and included in D6.3.

7.3 External events

Besides the already planned INFRAMIX workshops and the final event, several special sessions and workshops dedicated to INFRAMIX will also be organised in the framework of well-known conferences and congresses, such as the ITS European and World Congresses even from the 1st year of INFRAMIX.

INFRAMIX will be disseminated primarily through presentations and posters at relevant transport sector conferences, workshops and special meetings of AUVSI, CEDR, the ASECAP days, etc. "Marketing-oriented" presentations will also be performed at industry events and trades. The project brochure and give-aways will be distributed on different occasions and posters will be displayed in exhibitions.

The following table lists relevant potential events for the coming years:

Table 10 – Potential events for INFRAMIX (updated)

Event	Date	Place
Transportation Research Board Annual Meeting	Jan 2019	Washington, USA
Mobile World Congress	Feb (annual)	Barcelona, Spain
Intertraffic	Mar 2019	Amsterdam, NL
CIHT Annual Conference	Mar 2019	London, UK
IEEE Vehicular Technology Conference	Apr 2019	Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia
International Transport Forum (ITF)	May 2019	Leipzig, Germany
ASECAP Days	May 2019	Costa Navarino, Greece
Autonomous Vehicle Test & Development	May 2019	Stuttgart, Germany
ITS European Congress	Jun 2019	Brainport, NL
The Future of Transportation conference	Jul 2019	Köln, Germany
AVS 2019, Orlando	Jul 2019	Orlando, USA
ITS World Congress	Oct 2019	Singapore
IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Conference	Oct 2019	New Zealand
IOT Solutions World Congress	Oct (annual)	Barcelona, Spain
Smart Mobility Congress	Nov 2019	Barcelona, Spain
Highways UK	Nov 2019	Birmingham, UK
PIARC World Road Congress	Oct 2019	Abu Dhabi
TRA Transport Research Arena	Apr 2020	Helsinki, Finland
ECTRI	N/A	N/A
European Transport Forum	N/A	N/A

8. Measuring the effectiveness of activities

8.1 Summary of Key performance indicators

The effectiveness of INFRAMIX strategic approach and planning for communication and dissemination has been evaluated through dedicated performance indicators that are shown in Table 11. A final update will be reported in D6.7.

Table 11 - INFRAMIX Key Performance Indicators for Communication & Dissemination

Activity and criteria (KPI)	Expected performance			Real M18	
	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3		
Definition of Communication Strategy and Tools (Task 6.1)	Communication Strategy & plan: Annual project review	Positive	Positive (update)	Positive (update)	Positive
	Website – number of visitors (unique, returning)	250/month	400/month	400/month	117,3/average per month
	Twitter – total number of followers	100	150	200	139
	LinkedIn – total members of group members	80	120	180	49
	Social Media Campaigns –total number	1	1		2
	No of project videos – total number	≥ 0	≥ 1	≥ 1 (Updated)	1
	Quantity of media coverage achieved ³	≥ 10	≥ 10	≥ 20	Paper: 21 Online: 100 ⁴
Dissemination and communication to community (Task 6.2)	No of peer reviewed publications	≥ 3	≥ 7	≥ 8	3
	Readership results	150	200	350	270 ⁵
	No of End Users attending INFRAMIX workshops		≥ 40	≥ 40	-
	No of project events in conferences/congresses	≥ 1	≥ 2	≥ 2	12
	No of presentations	≥10	≥18	≥20	20
	No of demonstrations/exhibitions		≥1	≥2	-
	No of final event attendees			≥ 100	-
	No of Public & Media attending Final event ⁶			≥ 10	-
Networking/ User engagement activities (Task 6.3)	No of End User Group participants	≥ 20	≥ 60	≥ 100	26
	No of industry representatives involved	≥ 5	≥ 10	≥ 15	6
	No of associations & organisations involved	≥ 3	≥ 5	≥6	4
	No of projects contacted	≥ 8	≥ 8	≥ 10	13
	No of liaison activities performed	≥ 5	≥ 10	≥ 10	9
	No of discussions in fora, committees & organisations	≥ 5	≥ 5	≥ 5	10
	No of Standardisation bodies reached	≥2	≥2	≥2	2

After a first analysis of the performance for this first period, it seems that overall impact of the dissemination and communication strategy is aligned with the initial expectations. However, it is necessary to highlight some questions:

³ Number of media appearances

⁴ It must be noted that most of the media impact has been generated at Spanish coverage

⁵ We estimate the readership results according to the conference's attendees, as the papers are included in the conferences' minutes.

⁶ Number of different individuals or entities

- most of the impact have been created in Spain, Greece and Austria (in the latter case, taking into consideration the population of the country) compared to the impact in Germany. This should be re-addressed by enhancing the collaboration with the German partners, aligning their marketing departments.
- LinkedIn communication channel (INFRAMIX group) that it is analyzed on Section 8.3.2.

8.2 Analysis of INFRAMIX Website impact

8.2.1 Summary of the contents

The INFRAMIX project website content is related to the team and partners activities, both general and technical information about the project and is used as a channel to communicate the latest news and project outcomes. Since the website launch the INFRAMIX dissemination team and partners have posted relevant project content:

- 12 press releases and news have been published with information related to the partners' activities, such as conferences, congresses, workshops attended, etc.
- Two major events were covered by the dissemination team: Transport Research Conference in Europe (April 2018) and 25th ITS World Congress in Copenhagen (September 2018). A pre and post event press releases and social media coverage were specially implemented for these major events, according the relevance.
- Dissemination materials have been also published and shared with the major audience. A leaflet, banner, brochure and a paper description are available.
- A list of public deliverables is also available.
- Six presentations and four publications have been realized.
- The project scenarios and use cases are uploaded on the website with corresponding explanations.
- The two test sites are also described: the Spanish and Austrian, including relevant description diagrams and videos.
- One INFRAMIX project introduction video was uploaded to the brand-new YouTube channel and also embedded on the website.
- Two newsletters have been published (Jul'18 and Nov'18).

8.2.2 Visitor behaviour

The lapse of time analysed starts from October 2017, when the website went public, until September 2018. The INFRAMIX average number of visitors per month was 117,3 during the period from October 2018 to September 2018. This amount is quite low as a higher number of visitors was expected. The total of unique visitors from October 2017 to September 2018 was 1408 visits.

Table 12 - INFRAMIX Web site unique visitors in the period

Period	Unique visitors
Oct 2017 - May 2018	654
May - Sep 2018	754
Total unique visitors	1408
Average/month	117,3

Due to the application of GDPR⁷ (General Data Protection Regulation), the lapse of time analysed was split in two periods. The first one from October 2017 to May 2018 and the second one from May 2018 to September 2018.

Figure 4 – Visitors, visits, bounces and returning visits

As we can notice on this graphic, the website performance in June and July was highly better than the other analysed months during this period. The number of actions during these months contrasts with the number of unique visitors. This could indicate that the number of site visitors are not as high as expected but the audience is very well informed about the INFRAMIX project and want to know more about it. There is a noticeably interest in the project.

Figure 5 – Total minutes spent by all visitors for each month

The total time spent in the website by visitors was 943 minutes/month in average. The highest number of total minutes spent visiting the website was reached in June and July.

⁷ The analytical system to prepare the statistics of web use was updated after the application of GDPR (the regulation in EU law on data protection for all individuals within the European Union which became enforceable since 25 May 2018).

Figure 6 – Average session time for each month

In September, the average of time spent by the visitors was 9,68 minutes. This could indicate that visitors remain into the website for medium long sessions.

8.2.3 Performance and visitors per country

Figure 7 – Visits per country

As we can see, Spain has the biggest number of visits and the biggest number of actions is registered by Greece. This could be a result of the consortium partners' activity due to webmaster tasks. In terms of population and demographic statistics, there is a pending assignment for the German partners regarding the dissemination activities. Spain and Greece have less population than Germany and have the biggest performance stats.

Figure 8 – Total minutes spent by visitors by country

In terms of quantity of time spent visiting the website, Spain and Greece also have the biggest rate. Germany, Austria and United States hit the third and fourth place.

INFRAMIX website visitors remain in the site for much longer time from May 2018 and they are interested in the information they found on the website as they spend more time in the site. On the other hand, the number of visitors is much less than expected. Therefore, a more effective strategy must be defined in order to increase the interest within the target audiences who visit the site and also to gain new visitors.

8.3 INFRAMIX social networks

8.3.1 Twitter account @INFRAMIX

Figure 9 – Twitter account activity

Since the @Inframix account was launched in 22 May 2017 until 30 September 2018, 139 followers were reached. 6774,71 tweet impressions in average were reached during this period. During this lapse of time, the profile account had in average 45,82 profile visits, 4,29 mentions by other Twitter accounts and 7,94 new followers were interested in average on the INFRAMIX Twitter account.

Figure 10 – Twitter activity versus followers

An increasing trend is noticeable since February 2018 and it hit the highest peak during the months of April and September. INFRAMIX project participated on two major events during these months and the activity and social networking helped within this escalation. In addition, the number of followers reached is higher than expected. Twitter activity and interaction with the followers and other related accounts help increasing the INFRAMIX account notoriety.

Figure 11 – Twitter impact on audience

Social Mention on-line tool set as “neutral” the audience sentiment related to the keyword *Inframix* on a brief social media search. Twitter is the main social media source for the results as shown. The main *Inframix* keyword user is the Inframix project account (@inframix) followed by Enide Solutions (@enidesolutions).

8.3.2 LinkedIn Group

The INFRAMIX Project group has reached 50 members since its creation. This number is less than expected for the M18 (80). A much precise strategy could be suggested to increase the group notoriety and members’ engagement.

Some recommendations are:

- Invite the followers to join the LinkedIn Inframix group through Enide Solutions (as dissemination manager) LinkedIn page. Apply a cascade approach in order to extend the impact by using the networks of the INFRAMIX partners and team members
- Post the Inframix website and social media content on the LinkedIn group and invite the group members to like and share.
- Team members could help sharing the LinkedIn group posts on their own social media channels.

8.3.3 Google keywords ranking

Google Trends tool was used for a search query. The main keywords related to the project as *Inframix*, *automated driving*, *mixed traffic* and *infrastructure for automated driving* and the results were as follows:

Figure 12 – INFRAMIX impact on internet

As we can see, *automated driving* reaches the research keyword first place by far over the other query keywords. *Mixed traffic* reaches the second place and *Inframix* the third-place. *Infrastructure for automated driving* reaches no results.

inframix project
Término de búsqueda

+ Comparar

Todo el mundo ▼ Últimos 12 meses ▼ Todas las categorías ▼ Búsqueda web ▼

Interés a lo largo del tiempo ?

Tu búsqueda no tiene suficientes datos para mostrar resultados.
Comprueba que todo esté escrito correctamente o prueba un término más general.

Figure 13 – INFRAMIX project keyword

If we search for the *Inframix project* keyword there are no results for this expression. This means that the project has not gained as much public awareness to search for it directly. Therefore, a more effective strategy will be defined in order to promote the project, increase the public awareness and make the visitors to look for updates of this project specifically.

8.4 Activities performed during the first 18 months of project

The following table lists all the dissemination actions have already been executed until M18:

Table 13 - INFRAMIX dissemination actions up to month 18

Date	Type/ Description/ Title	Audience	Countries addressed	Size of Audience	Partner responsible / involved
Jul'17	Press release: project kick-off	General	Global	Massive	All
Jul'17	AVS 2017, San Francisco, Break-out session (infrastructure classification scheme)	Industry, Technical, Scientific	Global	Targeted	ICCS
Oct'17	ITS WC SIS with CoExist and TransAID. See Annex VI	Industry, Technical, Scientific	Global	Targeted	ICCS
Jan'18	TRB Annual meeting	Industry, Technical, Scientific	Global	Extensive	ICCS
Apr'18	TRA invited session with CoExist and TransAID	Industry, Technical, Scientific, EC&EU stakeholders	European	200	ICCS, ATE
Apr'18	TRA paper for INFRAMIX & session	Industry, Technical, Scientific, EC&EU stakeholders	European	200	ICCS, ATE

Apr'18	INFRAMIX dissemination materials at the TRA booths of ASF, ATE and SIE	Industry, Technical, Scientific, EC&EU stakeholders	European	40+	ASF, ATE, SIE
Apr'18	Poster Session at Symposium on Research & Innovation for Connected and Automated Driving in Europe co-organized by CARTRE and SCOUT initiatives, brochure. Vienna, Austria	Industry, Technical, Scientific, EC&EU stakeholders	European	200+	ATE, ASF
Jun'18	ASECAP Days, Slovenia. INFRAMIX presentation	Industry, Technical, Scientific, EC&EU stakeholders	European	500	AAE
Jun'18	TISA General Assembly, Technical & Standardization Committee Meeting, BAWG, TPEG3 Workshop, Cologne, Germany	Industry, Technical	Global	40	BMW TOM
Aug'18	Trilateral cooperation of road operators AUT/SLO/HUN	Industry, Technical, Road operators	European	20	ASF
Aug'18	ERTRAC/CEDR workshop	Industry, Technical, Road operators	European	7	ASF
Aug'18	CEDR WG Infrastructure workshop	Industry, Technical, Road operators	European	15-20	ASF
Sep'18	ITSWC: infrastructure support levels for AD (ISAD) session. Copenhagen, Denmark	Industry, Technical, Scientific	Global	40 attendees in session, about 8 active people in contact due to the SIS presentation	ASF, AAE
Sep'18	ITSWC: TM 2.0 and hybrid infrastructure as enablers for MaaS in the context of automated transport. Copenhagen, Denmark	Industry, Technical, Scientific	Global	100	AAE
Sep'18	ITSWC: How road infrastructure can support the transition to automation and the coexistence of conventional and automated vehicles on the same network. Copenhagen, Denmark	Industry, Technical, Scientific	Global	10	ATE
Sep'18	INFRAMIX dissemination materials at the ITSC booths of ITS Austria. Copenhagen, Denmark	Industry, Technical, Scientific, EC&EU stakeholders	European	10-20	ASF, ATE

Sep'18	Trilateral conference at ZalaZone	Industry, Technical, Road operators	European	20-30	ASF
Oct'18	MAVEN expert group meeting	Industry, Technical, Scientific, EC&EU stakeholders	European	18	TUC
Oct'18	INFRAMIX at European Road Conference, session "Connected, Autonomous & Shared Mobility - Readyng our Road Network"	Industry, Technical, Scientific, EC&EU stakeholders	European	60	ICCS
Oct'18	C-ITS services for CCAD at the informal meeting of European transport and environment ministers: booth	Industry, Technical, Scientific, EC&EU stakeholders	European	5 EU countries	ASF
Nov'18	IRF Global R2T Conference, Assessment of Road Infrastructure advances for Mixed Vehicle Traffic flows: the INFRAMIX approach	Industry, Technical, Scientific, Stakeholders	Global	30	ICCS
Nov'18	Fraunhofer / LINKS Innvovation and Networking Days 2018: Poster session for INFRAMIX	Industry, Technical, Scientific, EC&EU stakeholders	European	50-60	ENI
Nov'18	TISA TAWG (Technical Applications Working Group)	Industry, Technical	Global	15	BMW TOM
Nov'18	ERTRAC: INFRAMIX presentation at the European Conference: Results from Road Transport Research in H2020 projects	Industry, Technical, Scientific, EC&EU stakeholders	European	45	ATE

9. Conclusion

Communication and Dissemination activities are of major importance for the INFRAMIX project and therefore a significant number of communication and dissemination activities are planned for its duration. To coordinate the activities there is a need for a concise strategy.

In this deliverable, after the execution of the strategy and plan designed for the INFRAMIX project during M1-M18 period, the results and the assessment of the impact have been analysed.

The general conclusion is that the performance and impact of the dissemination and communication strategy for INFRAMIX project during the first period (M1-M18) has been aligned with the initial expectations. Most of the KPIs have been successfully achieved and even overcome in some cases. The INFRAMIX partners have been very active while presenting the project in several scenarios and to different stakeholders at any level. However, it is necessary to highlight some questions:

- Impact has been created but very focused on some countries. This should be re-addressed by enhancing the collaboration among the partners in the consortium
- The LinkedIn communication channel (INFRAMIX group) can generate additional impact if it could work as a discussion forum.

Beyond these aspects, no major questions or changes of the communication and dissemination strategy are expected for the following months.

10. References

- [1] "Wikipedia, Wikipedia," [Online]. Available: <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia>.
- [2] INFRAMIX, "INFRAMIX Project Consortium Agreement," 2017.
- [3] INFRAMIX, "D1.1 Quality Management Plan," 2017.
- [4] INFRAMIX, "INFRAMIX Project Description of Work," 2017.
- [5] INFRAMIX, "D6.5 Exploitation Plans," 2018.

ANNEX I – H2020 guidelines

H2020 Dissemination Guidelines

For Horizon 2020 projects the reference document for communication, dissemination and exploitation activities is the Grant Agreement (GA), and namely Articles 29 (Dissemination of results — Open access — Visibility of EU funding) and 38 (Promoting the action — Visibility of EU funding).

Promoting the action — Visibility of EU funding: Communication activities by beneficiaries

Regarding article 38, these are the rules to follow:

Obligation to promote the action and its results

The beneficiaries must promote the action and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner.

Before engaging in a communication activity expected to have a major media impact, the beneficiaries must inform INEA.

Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Unless INEA requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:

(a) Display the EU emblem and

(b) Include the following text:

For communication activities: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 723265”.

For infrastructure, equipment and major results: “This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 723265”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from INEA.

This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use.

Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this agreement, the grant may be reduced.

Dissemination of results — Open access — Visibility of EU funding

Regarding article 29, these are the rules to follow:

Obligation to disseminate results

Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must — as soon as

possible — ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium).

A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries of — unless agreed otherwise — at least 45 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

Any other beneficiary may object within — unless agreed otherwise — 30 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests.

If a beneficiary intends not to protect its results, it may [...] need to formally notify the *Innovation and Networks Executive Agency (INEA)* before dissemination takes place.

Open access to scientific publications

Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- The terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- The name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- The publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- A persistent identifier.

Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Unless INEA requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

(a) Display the EU emblem and

(b) Include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 723265”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

For the purposes of their obligations under this agreement, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from INEA.

This does not however give them the right to exclusive use.

Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

Disclaimer excluding INEA responsibility

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that INEA is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this agreement, the grant may be reduced.

Open access to scientific publications

Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- The terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- The name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- The publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- A persistent identifier.

Communication versus Dissemination

Excerpt from <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/support/faqs/faq-933.html>

Dissemination is the public disclosure of the results of the project in any medium. Disclosure may sound passive, like a shop opening up, but it is an activity, like a shopkeeper attracting customers. It is a process of promotion and awareness-raising right from the beginning of a project. It makes research results known to various stakeholder groups (like research peers, industry and other commercial actors, professional organisations, policymakers) in a targeted way, to enable them to use the results in their own work. This process must be planned and organised at the beginning of each project, usually in a dissemination plan.

Communication means taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. The aim is to reach out to society as a whole and in particular to some specific audiences while demonstrating how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges.

ANNEX II - Other Social media

Facebook

Description

Facebook is a social networking service launched in February 2004, owned and operated by Facebook, Inc. Facebook has more than 2 billion monthly active users as of June 2017. As of April 2016, Facebook was the most popular social networking site in the world, based on the number of active user accounts. Users must register before using the site, after which they may create a personal profile, add other users as friends, and exchange messages, including automatic notifications when they update their profile. Additionally, users may join common-interest user groups, organized by workplace, school or college, or other characteristics.

Users can create profiles with photos, lists of personal interests, contact information, and other personal information. Users can communicate with friends and other users through private or public messages and a chat feature. They can also create and join interest groups and "like pages", some of which are maintained by organizations as a means of advertising. A 2012 Pew Internet and American Life study identified that between 20–30% of Facebook users are "power users" who frequently link, poke, post and tag themselves and others.

The like button is a social networking feature, allowing users to express their appreciation of content such as status updates, comments, photos, and advertisements.

Use

Given its popularity as social network, this tool could have an important role in the communication and dissemination activities. However, currently, the general profile of the user as well as its lack of focus on professional activities does **not recommend** this network for scientific or technical dissemination.

Wikipedia

Description

Wikipedia is a collaboratively edited, multilingual, free Internet encyclopaedia supported by the non-profit Wikimedia Foundation. Its 24 million articles, over 4.1 million in the English Wikipedia, are written collaboratively by volunteers around the world. Almost all of its articles can be edited by anyone with access to the site. [...] It has become the largest and most popular general reference work on the Internet, ranking sixth globally among all websites on Alexa and having an estimated 365 million readers worldwide. [1]

Use

Although it is not a social network, Wikipedia is seen by many as a key entrance point for the understanding of scientific and technical concepts. In this way, it could be interesting to include a page to explain the project, the goals, achievements and updates, with emphasis in the following factors:

- Technical concepts related to the issues of the project: inductive charging, electric vehicles, batteries, etc
- Other internet tools related to the project (Twitter, LinkedIn, Web site, etc.)

Given the nature and rules of Wikipedia, especially concerning the revision and approval procedures, it is important to avoid that the entry in Wikipedia may have seen as just a promotion page, so both contents and language use should be carefully used. In addition,

Wikipedia is a tertiary information source, which is fed by secondary information sources (independent from the primary information source, which are the originators of the information). This means that before establishing a Wikipedia entry, several secondary information sources should inform about INFRAMIX.

SlideShare

Description

SlideShare is a Web 2.0 based slide hosting service. Users can upload files privately or publicly in the following file formats: PowerPoint, PDF, Keynote or OpenDocument presentations. Slide decks can then be viewed on the site itself, on hand held devices or embedded on other sites. Launched on October 4, 2006, the website is considered to be similar to YouTube, but for slideshows. The website was originally meant to be used for businesses to share slides among employees more easily, but it has since expanded to also become a host of a large number of slides that are uploaded merely to entertain. Although the website is primarily a slide hosting service, it also supports documents, PDFs, videos and webinars. SlideShare also provides users the ability to rate, comment on, and share the uploaded content...

SlideShare was voted among the World's Top 10 tools for education & e-learning in 2010.

On May 2012, SlideShare announced that it was to be acquired by LinkedIn.

Use

Although it was originally not a social network, SlideShare is seen by many as a key entrance point for the understanding of scientific and technical concepts. In this way, it could be interesting to include a page to explain the project, the goals, achievements and updates, with emphasis in the following factors:

In this case, it is foreseen that presentations material related to the project findings should be made available. Using the SlideShare functionalities, a channel with its followers could become a platform for disseminating the project by sharing the public presentations to a wider audience, as well as an additional starting point for the audience, by using the right terms for the search.

Open access repository

Description

According Wikipedia an open access repository is a digital platform that holds research output and provide free, immediate and permanent access to research results to anyone to use, download and distribute. To facilitate open access such repositories must be interoperable according to the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH). Search engines harvest the content of open access repositories, constructing a database of worldwide, free of charge available research.

Use

As opposed to simple institutional repository or disciplinary repository open access repositories provides free access to research to users outside the institutional community are one of the recommended ways to achieve the open access vision described in the Budapest Open Access Initiative definition of open access. This is sometimes referred to as "green" route to open access.

Following the H2020 rules regarding the publication of Dissemination information, including documents, articles and datasets (if any is available), INFRAMIX will publish its information in a permanent Open Access repository. At the current moment the initial candidates

include: ZENODO (a joint initiative of OpenAIRE and the CERN), Digital Commons, OALibrary (Open Access Library) or Open-Science-Repository. Among other considerations, being ready to be indexed by Google Scholar will be an important factor in the election.

ANNEX III – Data Privacy aspects concerning dissemination

This section describes the handling of data privacy in the dissemination activities.

After analysis of the impact of this question, it has been delimited to the management of the distribution mailing list of the INFRAMIX newsletter⁸. To fulfill the requirements on this aspect⁹ a specific procedure for the management of privacy of subscribed recipients of the Newsletter:

- The INFRAMIX partner responsible of the web platform management and hosting (ICCS) has confirmed that they are aligned with the Greek regulations for data protection (and as a result, they are aligned with the European regulations).
- For registration in the newsletter, subscribers will either:
 - register by themselves in the newsletter using the web registration form; or
 - if an INFRAMIX partners wants to invite one contact, she/he will redirect this contact to the registration form

Therefore, all contacts are only handled by one single partner, ICCS, so transfer of personal data among different partners is not necessary. In addition, ICCS will be the responsible to enable the right of modification and removal of the data included in the mailing list.

- Finally, whenever it is decided to share a communication with the list of people registered (i.e.: a newsletter), the INFRAMIX partner will submit the necessary materials to ICCS and they proceed with the mail distribution, to avoid data sharing.

⁸ Other aspects as data related to social networks (Twitter and LinkedIn in the case of INFRAMIX) are supported by the respective “terms and conditions” contracts of these platforms

⁹ General Data Protection Regulation:

http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/DE/TXT/?uri=uriserv%3AOJ.L_.2016.119.01.0001.01.DEU&toc=OJ%3AL%3A2016%3A119%3ATOC